

FRUCTOSE: FRIEND OR FOE?

To some fructose is the key performance elixir, high consumption rates of which when combined with other carbohydrates offering an immediate improvement in endurance performance. A similar hexose sugar to glucose and getting its name from fruit where it can be found naturally in relatively high concentrations, what's not to like?

In parallel with studies using increasing fructose concentrations in energy drinks and gels there has been an intense focus in the medical journals on the negative consequences of fructose consumption. High rates of fructose consumption especially via crystalline fructose and high fructose corn syrup have been linked to cardiovascular disease,

hypertension, diabetes, cancer, uric acid production and non-alcoholic liver disease. (Johnson et al. 2010, White 2013)

The latest study hanging a cloud over fructose was conducted by the Beckman Institute for Advanced Science and Technology at the University of Illinois (Rendero et al 2015), they tried to answer if an increase in fructose intake contributes to obesity in the absence of excessive calorie intake. The results from this study are perhaps some of most unlikely to translate into claims for fructose containing sports drinks. They concluded that matched calorie for calorie with the simple sugar glucose, fructose causes significant weight gain, physical inactivity and body fat deposition: not the kind of

attributes normally associated with improved performance.

This study is important because it starts to question a line often presented by the soft drink industry, that a calorie is a calorie and there is little difference in the metabolic fate relative to how the calories are consumed. Despite its structural similarity to glucose,

the body processes fructose very differently. The researchers in the Illinois study drew attention to how contrary to glucose, fructose bypasses certain metabolic steps and that this results in an increase in fat formation, especially in adipose tissue and liver.

That the body processes these sugars differently is exactly why they are so interesting to exercise scientists and sports performers. Whilst it is generally accepted that carbohydrate supplementation during exercise improves performance there is still much debate as to the optimum composition of sugars within those supplements.

Early energy drinks were mostly glucose based and research suggested there was little benefit to supplementing at levels greater than 60g per hour. This, it was thought, was due the carbohydrate transporters involved in the absorption of glucose being saturated at these levels. Fructose uses different transporters than glucose and may have a catalytic effects on carbohydrate absorption at low concentrations, so it is logical that combinations of both sugars are likely to deliver more carbohydrate to working muscles.

Whilst it was widely recognized that combinations of different sugars were likely to be beneficial to performance it was not until relatively recently that research attempts to quantify the likely benefits were conducted. Following the lead of Canadian researchers (Adopo et al 1985) the University of Birmingham conducted a whole series of experiments measuring the contribution of multiple transportable carbohydrates to energy production during exercise. (Jentjens et al. 2004a, Jentjens 2004b, Jeukendrup et al. 2005).

The Birmingham researchers make a compelling case for the inclusion of multiple transportable carbohydrates into energy supplements. In probably the most widely quoted paper they were able to show peak energy contributions of 105g per hour when 50:50 mixtures of glucose and fructose were consumed at an average rate of 144g per hour. This was significantly more than when glucose monohydrate was consumed at half this rate and much higher than previous thinking thought possible. (Jentjens & Jeukendrup 2005)

Although the highest energy contributions have been provided by high concentrations of glucose and fructose in a 1:1 ratio, most recent research focused on 2:1 ratios and these ratios have been widely employed in commercial formulations. Following on from

mechanistic studies a number of researchers have compared 2:1 formulations consumed at high rates with glucose monohydrate solutions concluding that it may offer a performance advantage in certain situations.

Other researchers have suggested that any performance advantage is more to do with the poor tolerance of the comparator drink. Invariably the comparator drink has been concentrated glucose monohydrate. Most commercial glucose based energy drinks are designed to work at approximately 6% solution since when consumed at higher 'hypertonic' concentrations they tend to slow gastric emptying causing bloating and nausea. Comparator glucose drinks were similar to isotonic drinks made at 3 times the recommended concentration

and then consumed at high rates. Unsurprisingly perhaps, they were not well tolerated, and in some of the early studies participants were sick or unable to finish them.

There is little data to suggest that high fructose drinks offer any performance advantage over more moderate or fructose free formulations when consumed at typically recommended levels.

One of the main advantages of high fructose formulations for the energy drink formulator is that they are intrinsically very sweet since fructose is approximately twice as sweet as sugar. However, for these formulations to offer any performance advantage over traditional glucose based drinks they need to be consumed at high rates. The obvious consequence of this is that fructose consumption reaches levels that many would regard as dangerous.

The widely published endocrinologist Robert Lustig who famously described fructose as 'like alcohol but without the buzz' suggests that consuming more than 50g of fructose per day is toxic (Lustig 2013). In comparison, researchers administered 95g of fructose in little more than an hour, and more than three times the suggested toxic dose in a 2.5 hour study to prove the ergogenic potential of these formulations.

Consumption rates such as these are likely to concern even those often opposed to Lustig's alarmist statements, recognizing that fructose can cause adverse metabolic effects when consumed either in doses much higher than normal daily amounts, or ratios to glucose greater than 1:5. (White 2013)

Many may hope that exercise will offer protection against any adverse effects of fructose consumption, after all the whole point of delivering the energy is to train or race harder. However, a 1999 study from the Spanish University of Cordoba suggests that exercise may not convey any immunity to the adverse effects of fructose consumption. In

their study they gave glucose or glucose and fructose before either endurance or resistance exercise. They found that the addition of fructose resulted in increased oxidative stress and inflammatory markers irrespective of the type of exercise performed.

High fructose drinks may however be hard to give up since fructose has been shown to differentially effect reward centers of the brain compared to glucose, so it may have addictive properties. In some ways stimulation of reward centers of the brain may have potential benefits to improve mood and possibly sports performance. However research just published in the Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences suggests that fructose consumers may become more interested in more food than other rewards. In their study (Lou et al 2015) human volunteers were more willing to give up monetary reward to obtain immediate high calorie food after consuming fructose than after consuming the same amount of energy in glucose.

Whilst fructose may therefore increase the likelihood of remembering to eat regularly during races, it may have

unexpected consequences on every day training decisions. Applying this recent work would suggest that faced with either completing those difficult hill reps or stopping at the café for cake, people may be more likely to take the cake option after consuming a high fructose gel for instance.

There is a sound rationale for the inclusion of fructose into sports drinks but it is possible to consume too much of a good thing. Riders should question whether they are in a situation to benefit from high fructose formulations, or if consumption has been influenced by the less savory aspects of this unique sugar. In many situations it may be possible to optimize performance with more moderate or even fructose free formulations.

Those wishing to utilize high fructose drinks should think about reducing their fructose load in the rest of their diet. In particular it is possibly good general nutrition advice to limit the consumption of high fructose corn syrup soft drinks and confectionary.

Generally, there is no need to reduce the consumption of real fresh fruit. Natural fruit contains natural anti-oxidant phytonutrients that regulate the absorption of carbohydrate and protect against inflammation, so it is quite different than high fructose corn syrup or crystalline fructose. Possibly more importantly, in its natural form it is often difficult to consume high quantities of fructose via real fruit. An apple contains approximately 10g of fructose but how many could you eat in one sitting? It is however worth considering the fructose and calorie contribution of those 'healthy' fruit juices and smoothies.

All references available: SPORTIFMAGAZINE.COM/REFERENCES

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BUT WITHOUT
THE BUZZ
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